

Bionomics of vectors and dynamics of rice yellow mottle virus in Tanzania

O.O. Banwo and R.H. Makundi, Sokoine University of Agriculture, P.O. Box 3005, Morogoro; R.S. Abdallah, Tropical Pesticides Research Institute, P.O. Box 3024, Arusha; J.C. Mbapila, Agricultural Research Institute, P.M.B. Ifakara, Tanzania
E-mail: banwo@hotmail.com

Rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV) is the only known viral disease of rice in Africa and it is endemic to the continent. It is now the most important disease of rice in Tanzania and is commonly found in lowland rice, which accounts for 80% of the country's rice production. The disease was first observed in Tanzania and Zanzibar in the early 1980s but has only lately drawn research attention. Ali (1999) and Luzi-Kihupi et al (2000) reported that RYMV has been observed in most of the major rice-growing regions in Tanzania and that the disease is spreading at an alarming rate between and within these regions. RYMV is transmitted efficiently by chrysomelid beetles (Bakker 1974). The important vectors in Tanzania are *Chaetocnema* sp. (a yet to be described species), *C. pulla* Chapuis, and *Dactylispa* sp. (not *Dactylispa bayoni* Gestro) (Banwo et al 2000). However, *Dactylispa* sp. is believed to be a potentially important vector since it is not found in all RYMV fields.

Nwilene (1999) reported that the dynamics of virus spread and the role of vectors are still poorly understood. To understand the dynamic nature of RYMV, studies on the bionomics of the vectors under two disease situations (hotspot and non-hotspot) were carried out. A good control measure depends on a thorough knowledge of virus epidemiology, vector bionomics, and ecology.

The experiment was conducted in the field in Ifakara in the Morogoro region. Four fields (replicates) were used for the two treatments (RYMV-infected/hotspot and no recorded history of RYMV infection/non-hotspot). Hotspot areas were chosen from places believed to be RYMV-infected, with a high rate of spread occurring consistently over the years. Non-hotspot areas were chosen from fields with no recorded history of RYMV. These fields (hotspot and non-hotspot) were within about a 1-km radius of one another. Each field (hotspot/non-hotspot) was in a different area. The selection was based on farmers' experience (of about 10 years) in relation to RYMV infection.

Traditional lowland rice variety Supa (susceptible to the disease), which requires 135–150 d of growth and is widely grown by farmers, was used. The broadcast system of planting is normally used for this variety. The crop was sown on 23 Jan 2000 under rainfed lowland conditions. Quadrats measuring 15 × 15 m were used in each selected field. The population of insect vectors (*Chaetocnema* sp. and *C. pulla*) was determined by taking 20 sweeps (with a sweep net) per quadrat biweekly from 21 to 91 d after planting (DAP). After this stage, there is less chance of RYMV infection to the crop. Populations of insect vectors of these two treatments were compared with each

other over time.

The figure shows statistically significant differences ($P < 0.05$) between the *Chaetocnema* sp. population in hotspot and non-hotspot areas at 35 and 49 DAP, with a higher vector population in hotspot areas. Also, highly statistically significant differences ($P < 0.001$) were obtained at 63, 77, and 91 DAP. For *C. pulla*, the difference in vector population was highly statistically significant ($P < 0.001$) only at 63 DAP, with a higher vector population in non-hotspot areas. Results of the regular sampling of vectors (*Chaetocnema* sp.

Population of *Chaetocnema* sp. and *C. pulla* in rice yellow mottle virus areas.

and *C. pulla*) in two RYMV areas (hotspot and non-hotspot) clearly showed that there was a higher population of *Chaetocnema* sp. in hotspots than in non-hotspot areas and that this difference increased with time. Thus, the population of the novel species *Chaetocnema* partly explains the difference in infection between the two RYMV areas. Other factors such as farmers' practices, elevation, and surrounding nonrice vegetation are the same

for both the hotspot and non-hotspot areas selected.

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Mortality of first- and second-instar larvae of yellow stem borer in four indica cultivars at the vegetative stage

E. Rubia-Sanchez, J. Catindig, and K.L. Heong, IRRI E-mail: e.sanchez@cgiar.org

At the tillering stage, larvae of the yellow stem borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker) cause deadhearts after about 1 wk of feeding inside the leaf sheath. At the preheading stage, larvae cause whiteheads after about 4 d of feeding inside the panicle stem. Cultivars that cause high early mortality of YSB larvae are good sources of resistance for breeding programs because many larvae will be killed before they have done sufficient feeding to cause deadheart or whitehead. In this study, we compared early larval mortality of YSB on four indica cultivars.

IR36, IR40, IR62, and IR72 rice seedlings were transplanted in a screenhouse at the rate of two seedlings hill⁻¹. One month after transplanting, hills were transferred into 13-cm-diam pots (one hill pot⁻¹) and caged in a greenhouse. There were four replicates for each cultivar. One egg mass (130–135 eggs; approximately 5 ×

4 mm) was placed on a hill in each cage. Three days after egg hatching, plants were uprooted from pots and stored at ambient temperature for 0–24 h before being dissected under a binocular microscope. Data were subjected to ANOVA and means were compared by LSD.

Larval mortality inside leaf sheaths was highest on IR40, followed by IR72 ($F = 4.68$, $df = 15$, $P < 0.05$; see figure). The cause of larval death is unknown but may be due to chemicals produced by plants in response to feeding. Further work will be done to identify these chemicals. IR40 and IR72 also had the lowest numbers of larvae recovered hill⁻¹ ($F = 21.32$, $df = 15$, $P < 0.01$). IR40 also had more tillers with no larvae ($F = 24.30$, $df = 15$, $P < 0.01$) because there were only a few larvae in the hill. The most susceptible cultivar, IR62, had an average of 6.2 larvae tiller⁻¹ with 92% live larvae hill⁻¹, whereas IR40 showed only 1.6 lar-

Larval mortality (%), total larvae (no.), and tillers (%) without larvae of four indica cultivars 3–4 d after egg hatching. Vertical lines indicate standard error.